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BACHELOR OF SCIENCE IN ELECTRICAL AND ELECTRONIC ENGINEERING

PROTOTYPE SUBSTATION DESIGN

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Submitted To

DEPARTMENT OF ELECTRICAL & ELECTRONIC ENGINEERING
UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY CHATTOGRAM

JULY 2022

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**In partial fulfillment of the requirement for the degree of Bachelor of Science
in Electrical & Electronic Engineering, University of Science & Technology
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Declaration:

“No portion of work presented in the thesis has been submitted in support of another award or qualification either at this institution or elsewhere”

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ABSTRACT

The electrical power system used today is a.c. i.e. alternating current is used to produce, transmit, and distribute electricity. Through a vast network of transmission and distribution, the electric power is at convenient locations, typically far away.

It may be essential and desired to alter certain electric supply properties (such as voltage, AC to DC conversion, frequency, and power factor, among others) at various points along the power system's line. A suitable piece of equipment called a substation carries out this function. The substation is the collection of equipment utilized for this. Similar to this, the voltage may need to be stepped down to the utilization level close to the consumer's locations. Once more, a suited tool called a substation handles this task.

Designing a substation and demonstrating the functionality of the major and secondary distribution systems are the primary goals of this project. Step up and step down, substation metering, load balancing, safety, and power quality were the main areas of concentration. We used an Arduino Board, a flame sensor, transformers, various sorts of sensors, an LED bulb as a load, electronic switches, an LCD display, a potentiometer, and other things in this project. We used the C++ programming language to carry out this project and simulated it on Proteus. This prototype substation has the capacity to alter the voltage and other properties of the electrical energy passing through it, as well as to interrupt or create an electrical circuit. This project will describe the various equipment used in substations as well as their uses and functions. A system based on hardware has been created, and it has proven that the system is effective.

Keyword: General arrangement, Microcontroller, Controlling device, Electrical Protective devices, Arduino UNO, Programming.

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

An electrical substation is an integral part of a generation, transmission and distribution system. A substation can interrupt or establish electrical circuit, change the voltage, frequency or other characteristics of electrical energy flowing in the circuit. It is common to refer to the transmission and distribution elements as networks or again, as systems.^[9]

Depending on the size and complexity of a particular utility system, the transmission and/or distribution networks may include more than one voltage level.^[9]

Figure 1.1: Electrical Substation^[9]

For instance, a utility's transmission network may include 115 kV and 230 kV transmission lines, while another utility's distribution network may include both 13.8 kV and 34.5 kV distribution lines.^[9]

The substation provides the interconnection of transmission circuits and the transformation between the network of different voltages.^[9]

The substation is connected to the network through overhead lines. In some cases, it may not be possible to make a connection to the substation directly by the overhead line and underground cable entry must be considered. [9]

1.2 Electrical Substations have the following mission to accomplish:

- (a) Step-up and step-down voltage transformation

- (b) Connection of separate transmission and distribution lines into a system to increase efficiency and reliability of power supply.

- (c) Sectionalizing of the power system to increase its reliability and operational flexibility—substation called “switching substation”

The different substation configurations are characterized by their busbar arrangements and generally, any number of circuits may be provided by repeating the pattern.

1.3 Types of Substations

There are many kinds of ac substations. They are classified into different types based on various criteria. Some of them are discussed below.

Based on the construction and installation of switchgear, electric substations are of two types.

- (a) Air Insulated Switchgear Substation (Open Terminal Substation)
- (b) Gas Insulated Switchgear Substation (Metal Clad Substation)

Based on transmission voltage and function, the electric substation is classified into three types.

- (a) Transmission Substation
- (b) Sub transmission Substation
- (c) Distribution Substation

In addition to this, based on the installation premises there are four major types of substations.

- (a) Generating Substation
- (b) Customer Substation
- (c) System Station
- (d) Distribution Station
- (e) Switching Substation

Figure 1.2: Types of Substations ^[9]

✓ **Generating station substations** transform generation voltage (usually 15 kV through 23 kV) up to transmission network voltage (usually 69 kV through 500 kV). **Transmission switching substations** interconnect portions of the utility system transmission network but do not include transformation between voltage levels. ^[9]

✓ **Transmission step-down** (or step-up, depending on your point of view) substations interconnect portions of the utility system transmission network and include transformation between transmission network voltage levels. ^[9]

✓ **Distribution step-down substations** may or may not interconnect portions of the utility system transmission network, include transformation between transmission network and distribution network voltage levels, and interconnect portions of the utility system

distribution network. [9]

✓ **Distribution substations** interconnect portions of the utility system distribution network and may include transformation between distribution voltage levels. [9]

1.4 Functions of a Substation

A substation performs a major role in our power system. The functions of a substation may include one or more of the following:

- (a) To isolate a faulted element from the rest of the utility system.
- (b) To allow an element to be disconnected from the rest of the utility system for maintenance or repair.
- (c) To change or transform voltage levels from one part of the utility system to another.
- (d) To control power flow in the utility system by switching elements into or out of the utility system.
- (e) To provide sources of reactive power for power factor correction or voltage control.
- (f) To provide data concerning system parameters (voltage, current flow, power flow) for use in operating the utility system.

1.5 Substation Equipment / Components

An electrical substation contains many types of equipment. Substation generally comprises the following equipment:

- (a) Power Transformers
- (b) Tap Changing Equipment

- (c) Circuit Breakers
- (d) Busbar, Bays and Steel Structures
- (e) Lightning Arrester
- (f) Circuit Switchers
- (g) Disconnect Switch / Isolator
- (h) Earth Switches
- (i) Current Transformer
- (j) Potential Transformer
- (k) High-Voltage Fuses
- (l) Metal-Clad Switchgear
- (m) Shunt Reactors
- (n) Coupling Capacitor Voltage Transformer
- (o) Control House
- (p) Control Panel
- (q) Substation Protective Relays
- (r) Supervisory Control
- (s) Remote Terminal Unit
- (t) Digital Fault Recorder
- (u) Capacitor Bank
- (v) Voltage Regulator
- (w) Power-Line Carrier Equipment
- (x) Microwave Equipment
- (y) Batteries

To fulfill the function of a substation, they include a wide variety of equipment. Each of them will be explained in the next subsections.

1.5.1 Power Transformers

Power transformers are the most important equipment in an electrical substation. They are different from distribution transformers. They perform different functions. They are used to

- (a) Change the voltage from one level to another
- (b) To regulate the voltage level,
- (c) To control the flow of reactive kilovolt-amperes in the power system.

Power transformers installed in transmission substations will normally be constructed for and operate at voltages in the range of 138,000 volts to 765,000 volts or higher. Most substations will have three-phase transformers. Some substations will have three single-phase transformers in parallel installed in a bank. ^[9]

Figure 1.3: Power Transformer ^[9]

1.5.2 Circuit Breakers

High Voltage and Medium-voltage switchgear such as oil circuit breaker, SF6 circuit breaker, air circuit breaker, gas circuit breaker, and vacuum circuit breakers are used to switch electric circuits and substation equipment in and out of the system. ^[9]

A circuit breaker is a mechanical switching device, capable of making, carrying and breaking currents under normal circuit conditions and also making, carrying for a specified time and breaking currents under specified abnormal circuit conditions such as those of short circuit. ^[9]

The contacts of the circuit breakers are opened and closed by mechanical linkages manufactured from insulating materials and utilizing energy from compressed air, electric magnets, or charged springs. ^[9]

Figure 1.4: Circuit Breaker ^[9]

Various types of circuit breakers used in high voltage substations are.

- SF6 Circuit Breaker
- Oil Circuit Breaker
- Air Blast Circuit Breaker
- Vacuum Circuit Breaker

There are low voltage circuit breakers like MCB and GFCI that are not normally used in high voltage substations. MCBs are used inside the control panels. ^[9]

1.6 Capacitor Bank

Reactive kilovolt-amperes can be supplied to the electrical system by connecting banks of capacitors to the distribution circuits in substations or out on the distribution lines to neutralize the effect of customer-inductive loads. ^[9]

1.7 Voltage Regulator

The voltage regulators maintain the system voltage on the distribution circuits. As settings on the voltage regulators are adjusted for various load conditions that occur, the desired voltage is obtained. ^[9]

1.8 Project/Thesis Overview:

The remaining portion of this project is organized as follows:

- i. Chapter 1 represents the Introduction.
- ii. Chapter 2 represents the literature review.
- iii. Chapter 3 represents the experimental setup.
- iv. Chapter 4 represents the results and discussion.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Aim

This literature review is intended to help us understand the current project and discussions that are pertinent to a particular subject or field of study and to communicate that understanding in the form of a written report. We can increase our understanding of field by conducting a literature review.

2.1 Introduction

The **Arduino Uno** is an open-source microcontroller board based on the Microchip ATmega328P microcontroller and developed by Arduino.cc. The board is equipped with sets of digital and analog input/output (I/O) pins that may be interfaced to various expansion boards (shields) and other circuits. The board has 14 digital I/O pins (six capable of PWM output), 6 analog I/O pins, and is programmable with the Arduino IDE (Integrated Development Environment), via a type B USB cable. It can be powered by the USB cable or by an external 9-volt battery, though it accepts voltages between 7 and 20 volts. It is similar to the Arduino Nano and Leonardo. The hardware reference design is distributed under a Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike 2.5 license and is available on the Arduino website. Layout and production files for some versions of the hardware are also available.^{[1][6][8]}

The word "Uno" means "one" in Italian and was chosen to mark the initial release of Arduino Software. The Uno board is the first in a series of USB-based Arduino boards, it and version 1.0 of the Arduino IDE were the reference versions of Arduino, which have now evolved to newer releases. The ATmega328 on the board comes preprogrammed with a bootloader that allows uploading new code to it without the use of an external hardware programmer. While the Uno communicates using the original STK500 protocol, it differs from all preceding boards in that it does not use the FTDI USB-to-serial driver chip. Instead, it uses the Atmega16U2 (Atmega8U2 up to version R2) programmed as a USB-to-serial converter.^{[1][6][8]}

2.2 About Arduino UNO

A microcontroller is a microcomputer with few other application-specific devices on a single chip or VLSI core. It is an integrated part in a real-time control or communication system. It has the specified computational capabilities and the enhanced I/O operations capabilities. Henceforth a microcontroller will also be referred to an MCU. ^{[1][6][8]}

An MCU consists of a microcomputer circuit or unit with a provision to run in power-down mode or idle mode. ^{[1][6][8]}

Figure 2.0: Arduino UNO Board ^[8]

2.2.1 Internal Structure of a Microcontroller

Port devices along with bit-manipulation instructions processing by CPU, which enables control of the interfaced relays and switches. Synchronous and asynchronous serial I/O devices. Timer device for the system clock, real time clock, software timers, real time detection of an event or signal (compare the time or capture time on an event) and watch dog timer device. PWM device, ADC device, MODEM device. DSP ports with DSP instructions processing circuit at CPU. Ports with non-linear controller instructions processing at CPU. Ports with network interface and CPU processing instructions related to network processing. Ports with mobile or wireless interface and CPU capable of processing of processing related instructions. ^{[2][3][4]}

Figure 2.1: Internal Structure of a microcontroller

2.2.2 Types of Microcontrollers

Figure 2.2: Types of microcontroller ^[3]

2.3 Historical background

The ATmega328 is a single-chip microcontroller created by Atmel in the mega AVR family (later Microchip Technology acquired Atmel in 2016). It has a modified Harvard architecture 8-bit RISC processor core. ^{[2][3][4]}

2.4 Working of ATmega328

The Atmel 8-bit AVR RISC-based microcontroller combines 32 KB ISP flash memory with read-while-write capabilities, 1 KB EEPROM, 2 KB SRAM, 23 general purpose I/O lines, 32 general purpose working registers, three flexible timer/counters with compare modes, internal and external interrupts, serial programmable USART, a byte-oriented 2-wire serial interface, SPI serial port, 6-channel 10-bit A/D converter (8-channels in TQFP and QFN/MLF packages), programmable watchdog timer with internal oscillator, and five software selectable power saving modes. The device operates between 1.8-5.5 volts. The device achieves throughput approaching 1 MIPS per MHz. ^{[2][3][4]}

2.5 The outline of ATmega328

Figure 2.3: The outline of ATmega328

2.6 Pin diagram of ATmega328

Figure 2.4: Pin Diagram of PIC16F877A ^[4]

2.7 IR Module

The IR sensor module consists mainly of the IR Transmitter and Receiver, Opamp, Variable Resistor (Trimmer pot), output LED in brief.

IR LED Transmitter^[6]

IR LED emits light, in the range of Infrared frequency. IR light is invisible to us as its wavelength (700nm – 1mm) is much higher than the visible light range. IR LEDs have light emitting angle of approx. 20-60 degree and range of approx. few centimeters to several feet's, it depends upon the type of IR transmitter and the manufacturer. Some transmitters have the range in kilometers. IR LED white or transparent in color, so it can give out amount of maximum light. ^[6]

Photodiode Receiver

Photodiode acts as the IR receiver as its conducts when light falls on it. Photodiode is a semiconductor which has a P-N junction, operated in Reverse Bias, means it start conducting the current in reverse direction when Light falls on it, and the amount of current flow is proportional

to the amount of Light. This property makes it useful for IR detection. Photodiode looks like a LED, with a black color coating on its outer side, Black color absorbs the highest amount of light. LM358 Opamp. LM358 is an Operational Amplifier (Op-Amp) is used as voltage comparator in the IR sensor. the comparator will compare the threshold voltage set using the preset (pin2) and the photodiode's series resistor voltage (pin3).^[6]

Photodiode's series resistor voltage drop > Threshold voltage = Opamp output is High

Photodiode's series resistor voltage drop < Threshold voltage = Opamp output is Low

When Opamp's output is **high** the LED at the Opamp output terminal **turns ON** (Indicating the detection of Object).^{[2][3][4]}

Variable Resistor

The variable resistor used here is a preset. It is used to calibrate the distance range at which object should be detected.

Figure 2.5: IR Module^[6]

2.8 LED Module

A light-emitting diode (LED) is an electronic light source. The LED was first invented in Russia in the 1920s, and introduced in America as a practical electronic component in 1962. LEDs are based on the semiconductor diode. When the diode is forward biased (switched on), electrons are able to recombine with holes and energy is released in the form of light. This effect is called electroluminescence and the color of the light is determined by the energy gap of the

semiconductor. The LED is usually small in area (less than 1 mm^2) with integrated optical components^[6]

Figure 2.6: LED Module^[6]

Figure 2.7: Internal Function of LED^[6]

2.8.1 Applications of LEDs fall into four major categories

- a) Visual signal application where the light goes more or less directly from the LED to the human eye, to convey a message or meaning.
- b) Illumination where LED light is reflected from object to give visual response of these objects.
- c) Generate light for measuring and interacting with processes that do not involve the human visual system.
- d) Narrow band light sensors where the LED is operated in a reverse-bias mode and is responsive to incident light instead of emitting light.

2.9 Buzzer

A **buzzer** or **beeper** is an audio signaling device, which may be mechanical, electromechanical, or piezoelectric (*piezo* for short). Typical uses of buzzers and beepers include alarm devices, timers, and confirmation of user input such as a mouse click or keystroke. Piezoelectric buzzers, or piezo buzzers, as they are sometimes called, were invented by Japanese manufacturers and fitted into a wide array of products during the 1970s to 1980s. This advancement mainly came about because of cooperative efforts by Japanese manufacturing companies. In 1951, they established the Barium Titanate Application Research Committee, which allowed the companies to be "competitively cooperative" and bring about several piezoelectric innovations and inventions.^[11]

While technological advancements have caused buzzers to be impractical and undesirable, there are still instances in which buzzers and similar circuits may be used. Present day applications include:

- (a) Novelty uses
- (b) Judging panels
- (c) Educational purposes
- (d) Annunciator panels
- (e) Electronic metronomes
- (f) Game show lock-out device
- (g) Microwave ovens and other household appliances
- (h) Sporting events such as basketball games
- (i) Electrical alarms
- (j) Joy buzzer (mechanical buzzer used for pranks)

Figure 2.8: Buzzer^[11]

CHAPTER 3

PROJECT METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter explains the methodology that was used in carrying out the project work. Crucial issues that were discussed in this chapter includes, project design, simulation circuit, simulation process, data collection, and techniques and ethical considerations.

3.1.1 Block Diagram

Figure 3.1: Block diagram of Prototype Substation

3.2 Circuit Simulation in Proteus

Figure 3.2: Circuit Diagram of Prototype Substation

3.3 Working Principle of the project

In this project we will focus into four functions mainly.

i) **Step up & Step-down process-** For step up process here we used two transformer TR2 and TR4. Generating voltage of generating station 1 is 27.03KV (demo) and 27.03KV (demo) for generating station 2. TR2 and TR4 will increase voltage as step-up transformer. Similarly, TR1 and TR3 are distributive transformer or step-down transformer for using as distributive transformer. Finally, if we ON the logic state switch then we will see the step up and step-down voltage on display. We can regulate voltages by RV1 and RV2. The voltage regulators maintain the system voltage on the distribution circuits. As settings on the voltage regulators are adjusted for various load conditions that occur, the desired voltage is obtained.

ii) **Substation metering:** In this section we will show the total voltage of generating station 1 & 2 by regulating RV1 or RV2. If we regulate RV1 or RV2 then the total voltage will be changed according to voltage regulator. And it will be shown in display. Here we can generate max 54.06KV (demo) In distributive section we used rectifier to control electronic controlling devices such as, display unit, Arduino uno board, flame sensor etc. But in load section we will use AC load by using of relay.

iii) **Load balancing:** According to our substation design if we increase generation of voltage then we can use maximum of loads, similarly if we minimize generation of electricity then we cannot use maximum loads. In this project 54.06KV (demo) is maximum generation and in this situation, we can use maximum loads in city and village area. In this project we showed load balancing properly and display unit will show the voltage of generation and consumption at the same time.

iv) **Capacitor banking:** Reactive kilovolt-amperes can be supplied to the electrical system by connecting banks of capacitors to the distribution circuits in substations or out on the distribution lines to neutralize the effect of customer-inductive loads. By removing the voltage drop in the system caused by inductive reactive loads, capacitors used in this manner help to manage voltages provided to the customer. In this project we used capacitor bank help to control voltages supplied to the customer by eliminating the voltage drop in the system caused by inductive reactive loads.

3.4 Software Specification

- i. **Arduino IDE**
- ii. **Proteus**

3.4.0 Arduino IDE Software

The Arduino IDE is an open-source software, which is used **to write and upload code to the Arduino boards**. The IDE application is suitable for different operating systems such as Windows, Mac OS X, and Linux. It supports the programming languages C and C++. The Arduino Integrated Development Environment - or Arduino Software (IDE) - contains a text editor for writing code, a message area, a text console, a toolbar with buttons for common functions and a series of menus. It connects to the Arduino hardware to upload programs and communicate with them.

Figure 3.3: Arduino IDE software ^[1]

3.4.1 Writing Sketches

Programs written using Arduino Software (IDE) are called **sketches**. These sketches are written in the text editor and are saved with the file extension. `.ino`. The editor has features for cutting/pasting and for searching/replacing text. The message area gives feedback while saving and exporting and also displays errors. The console displays text output by the Arduino Software (IDE), including complete error messages and other information. The bottom righthand corner of the window displays the configured board and serial port. The toolbar buttons allow you to verify and upload programs, create, open, and save sketches, and open the serial monitor.

3.4.2 Proteus Design Suit

The Proteus Design Suite is a proprietary software tool suite used primarily for electronic design automation. The software is used mainly by electronic design engineers and technicians to create schematics and electronic prints for manufacturing printed circuit boards.^[7]

The Proteus Design Suite is a Windows application for schematic capture, simulation, and PCB (Printed Circuit Board) layout design. It can be purchased in many configurations, depending on the size of designs being produced and the requirements for microcontroller simulation. All PCB Design products include an auto router and basic mixed mode SPICE simulation capabilities. The main components of Proteus Design Suite^[7]

This software includes two main components around which the program's entire functioning revolves:

ISIS: the acronym of Intelligent Schematic Input System. The program allows us to carry out the electric design of the circuit, including all sorts of components such as resistors, coils, capacitors, power supplies, and even microprocessors.[10]

ARES: the acronym of Advanced Routing and Editing Software. It's the tool aimed at the design of printed circuit boards or PCBs, with routing, location, and editing functions for electronic components.[10]

Figure 3.4: Proteus Design Suit^[7]

3.4.3 Schematic Capture

Schematic capture in the Proteus Design Suite is used for both the simulation of designs and as the design phase of a PCB layout project. It is therefore a core component and is included with all product configurations.

3.4.4 Microcontroller Simulation

The micro-controller simulation in Proteus works by applying either a hex file or a debug file to the microcontroller part on the schematic. It is then co-simulated along with any analog and digital electronics connected to it. This enables its use in a broad spectrum of project prototyping in areas such as motor control, temperature control and user interface design. It also finds use in the general hobbyist community and, since no hardware is required, is convenient to use as a training or teaching tool. Support is available for co-simulation of:

- a) Microchip Technologies PIC10, PIC12, PIC16, PIC18, PIC24, dsPIC33 microcontrollers
- b) Atmel AVR (and Arduino), 8051 and ARM Cortex-M3 microcontrollers
- c) NXP 8051, ARM7, ARM Cortex-M0 and ARM Cortex-M3 microcontrollers
- d) Texas Instruments MSP430, PICCOLO DSP and ARM Cortex-M3 microcontrollers
- e) Parallax Basic Stamp, Freescale HC11, 8086 microcontrollers

3.4.5 PCB Design

The PCB Layout module is automatically given connectivity information in the form of a netlist from the schematic capture module. It applies this information, together with the user specified design rules and various design automation tools, to assist with error free board design. PCB's of up to 16 copper layers can be produced with design size limited by product configuration

3.4.6 Project Management/Project Schedule Plan

Sample of work schedule is given below

Study of Literature	-04 weeks
Analysis of Proposed Scheme	-04 weeks
Preparation of Model	-04 weeks
Implementation of Model	-04 weeks

Analysis and Simulation -04 weeks
 Result Formulation -04 week
 Final Write-up & project Submission -08 weeks

Activity	October 2021	November 2021	December 2021	January 2022	February 2022	March 2022	April 2022	May 2022
Study of Literature								
Analysis of Proposed Project								
Preparation of Model								
Implementation of Model								
Analysis and Simulation								
Hardware Work								
Final work & Submission								

Table 1: Sample of work schedule

Budget: Experimental setup is present in university or some other organization's setup will be required for the execution of proposed project.

Cost Summary (Proposed)	
Develop work plan (Hardware)	Tk.25,000/00 – Tk.30,000/00

Table 2: Cost summary of the project

CHAPTER 4

EXPERIMENTAL RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Introduction:

Our project operates/controlled by manually. There are some knobs to control different function of the project.

Figure 4.0: Circuit Diagram of the project

4.2 Controlling & Monitoring Section Result

After turning on total system, the display and whole system will start working within second. Then measured any analog value of the system is being converted to digital value via Arduino, which we can see on display.

Figure 4.1: Practical Project Over view

When Generating Station-1 is working then we can see the generating value on display below, it's not fixed value as on display showing below. During Generation Station-1 is ON Generation Station will be off As required power.

Figure 4.2: Substation Generating

4.3 Generating Procedure

Here, we employed two transformers, TR2 and TR4, for the step-up process. The generating voltage for generating station 1 is 27.03 KV (demo), and for generating station 2, it is also 27.03 KV (demo). TR2 and TR4 will act as step-up transformers to enhance voltage. Similar to TR2, TR3 is a step-down transformer that can be used as a distributive transformer. Finally, the step up and step down voltages will be displayed if we turn on the logic state switch. RV1 and RV2 enable voltage control. On the distribution circuits, the voltage regulators keep the system voltage constant. The desired voltage is achieved as settings on the voltage regulators are altered for various load circumstances that occur.

When Generation Station-1 and Generating Station-2 working parallelly the total value of power will show on display as below. That mean total generation will be increased

Figure 4.3: Substation Metering

4.4 Substation metering

By controlling RV1 or RV2, we will display the combined voltage of producing stations 1 and 2 in this part. The overall voltage will change in accordance with the voltage regulator if RV1 or RV2 are regulated. Additionally, it will be displayed. Here, we can only produce up to 54.06KV (demo) to regulate electrical controlling devices like a display unit, an Arduino Uno board, a flame sensor, etc. in the distributive area, we employed a rectifier. However, we shall employ an AC load with a relay in the load part

Figure 4.4: Load Balancing

4.5 Load balancing:

In accordance with the substation design, we can use the maximum amount of loads if we increase voltage generation, but we cannot use the maximum amounts of loads if we reduce electricity output. The project's maximal generation, 54.06KV (demo), allows us to employ the highest loads in the city and rural areas. In this project, we demonstrated proper load balancing, and the display device would simultaneously display the voltage of generation and consumption.

After turning on load balancing switch we can supply to load and load will be ON. Output result or value will be shown on display as below. During load balancing we can also see the total generation power.

Figure 4.5: Capacitor Banking

4.6 Capacitor banking:

To counteract the impact of customer-inductive loads, banks of capacitors can be connected to distribution circuits in substations or out on the distribution lines and used to supply reactive kilovolt-amperes to the electrical system. Capacitors employed in this way assist in managing voltages supplied to the customer by reducing the voltage drop in the system brought on by inductive reactive loads. By removing the voltage drop in the system brought on by inductive

reactive loads, we were able to control the voltages supplied to the customer in this project with the aid of capacitor banks.

A capacitor bank is used for reactive power compensation and power factor correction in the power substations. Capacitor banks are mainly used to enhance the electrical supply quality and enhance the power systems efficiency.

CHAPTER - 5

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE ASPECTS

5.1 Conclusion

From our project findings we can finally conclude that the highest level of theoretical knowledge in practical section. This project can be successfully implemented in future to be installed in road junctions and have a great future scope.

5.2 Future Aspects

By implementation of this smart accident prevention system, the number of accidents occurring in curves of hills have not only reduced but also there is signal providing information that vehicles are coming from the opposite side, hence alerting us. This is an innovative approach. Moreover, there will be led signals alerting drivers to drive slow and consequently green signals to convey message that no vehicle is coming from the opposite.

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Abbreviations

LED- Light Emitting Diode

EPROM- Erasable programmable read only memory

PWM- Pulse Width Modulation

DSP- Digital signal processing

ADC- Analog-to-digital converter

EEROM- Electrically Erasable Read only memory

PIC- Peripheral interface controller

IR- Infrared Ray

Project Code

Language: C++

```
#include<Wire.h>
#define SD1 A0
#define SD2 A1
#define CB A2
#include<LiquidCrystal_I2C.h>
LiquidCrystal_I2C lcd(0x27,16,2);//0x27//0x3F//0x20
float lm_value;
float lm_value1;
float lm_value2;
float voltage;
float voltage1;
float voltage2;
void setup() {
  pinMode(2,INPUT);
  pinMode(3,INPUT);
  pinMode(4,INPUT);
  pinMode(5,INPUT);
  pinMode(6,OUTPUT);
  pinMode(7,OUTPUT);
  pinMode(8,OUTPUT);
  pinMode(9,OUTPUT);
  pinMode(10,OUTPUT);
  pinMode(11,OUTPUT);
  pinMode(12,OUTPUT);
  pinMode(13,INPUT);
  lcd.init();

}
```

```

void loop() {
  // Serial.begin(115200);
  lcd.setCursor(0,0);
  lcd.clear();
  lcd.print("Substation");
  delay(500);

  //Serial.println(voltage);
  lm_value = analogRead(SD1);
  voltage = (lm_value *50) /1023;
  lm_value1 = analogRead(SD2);
  voltage1 = (lm_value1 *50) /1023;
  float sum=voltage+voltage1;
  lm_value2 = analogRead(CB);
  voltage2 = (lm_value2 *25) /1023;
  if(digitalRead(2)==HIGH)
  {
    lcd.setCursor(0,1);
    lcd.print(voltage);
    lcd.setCursor(5,7);
    lcd.print("KV");
    delay(500);
  }
  if(digitalRead(2)==LOW)
  {
    lcd.clear();
  }
  if(digitalRead(3)==HIGH)
  {

  lcd.setCursor(0,1);

```

```

lcd.print(sum);
lcd.setCursor(5,7);
lcd.print("KV");
delay(500);
}
if(digitalRead(3)==LOW)
{
  lcd.clear();
}
if(digitalRead(4)==HIGH && digitalRead(13)==LOW)
{
  if(sum>=60)
  {
    digitalWrite(6,HIGH);
    digitalWrite(7,HIGH);
    digitalWrite(8,HIGH);
    digitalWrite(9,HIGH);
    digitalWrite(10,HIGH);
    digitalWrite(11,HIGH);
    digitalWrite(12,HIGH);
    lcd.setCursor(0,1);
    lcd.print("All area Run");
    delay(500);
  }
  else if(sum<=55 && sum>=53)
  {
    digitalWrite(6,HIGH);
    digitalWrite(7,HIGH);
    digitalWrite(8,HIGH);
    digitalWrite(9,HIGH);
    digitalWrite(10,HIGH);
    digitalWrite(11,LOW);

```

```

digitalWrite(12,LOW);
lcd.setCursor(0,1);
lcd.print("Load Balance");
delay(500);
}
else if(sum<=52)
{
digitalWrite(6,HIGH);
digitalWrite(7,LOW);
digitalWrite(8,HIGH);
digitalWrite(9,LOW);
digitalWrite(10,LOW);
digitalWrite(11,LOW);
digitalWrite(12,LOW);
lcd.setCursor(0,1);
lcd.print("Load off");
delay(500);
}
}
if(digitalRead(4)==LOW)
{
lcd.clear();
}
if(digitalRead(5)==HIGH)
{
lcd.setCursor(0,1);
lcd.print(voltage2);
lcd.setCursor(5,7);
lcd.print("KV");
delay(500);
}
}

```

```
if(digitalRead(5)==LOW)
{
  lcd.clear();
}
if(digitalRead(13)==HIGH && digitalRead(4)==HIGH )
{
  digitalWrite(6,LOW);
  digitalWrite(7,LOW);
  digitalWrite(8,LOW);
  digitalWrite(9,LOW);
  digitalWrite(10,LOW);
  digitalWrite(11,LOW);
  digitalWrite(12,LOW);
  lcd.clear();
  lcd.setCursor(0,0);
  lcd.print("Fire Occured");
  lcd.setCursor(0,1);
  lcd.print("Shutdown");
  delay(500);

}
}
```